

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SOCIALLY ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCE

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ANNOTATION

Enhancing social and civic skills in secondary education by utilizing and assessing instructional modules and educational settings.

Recent research conducted internationally in the field of social science teaching has highlighted the challenges faced by adolescents in developing their social and civic awareness, as well as their own sense of identity. To gain further insight into this process, this study focuses on social science classrooms in Spain and specifically examines how social and civic competence is fostered through different teaching methods and learning environments. The research specifically looks at democratic citizenship education, as it is widely acknowledged that it is an important objective of the educational system according to the theoretical and epistemological foundations of social sciences.

Key words: main goal, impact of implementing, teaching unit, social skill, civic skill, citizenship, classroom climate;

The main goal of this study is to assess the impact of implementing two teaching units on the development of social and civic skills among a group of 110 students in five secondary and high schools in Catalonia. A qualitative observational approach is utilized to observe, describe, and analyze the implementation and effects of these teaching units, adopting a hermeneutic-interpretative perspective. An ethnographic lens is applied to gather insights from education professionals and students. Furthermore, field notes are analyzed using software, focusing on two aspects: citizenship and classroom climate.

The study reveals two main findings. Firstly, it demonstrates the educational value of both instructional sequences in fostering democratic, active, and critical citizenship. Secondly, it highlights the significance of creating a conducive classroom environment through the design of tailored learning spaces and the implementation of active teaching methods to promote the development of responsible and engaged citizenship. The conclusions draw attention to two important aspects. Firstly, the subject of History at the secondary level should be recognized as a crucial tool for cultivating democratic awareness and fostering active and critical citizenship skills. Additionally, there is a correlation between the cultivation of critical and active citizenship and the

establishment of learning environments that encourage reflection, analysis, interpretation, and dialogue. The implications of this study present a significant challenge for the field of social sciences. It calls for a reevaluation of initial teacher training methodologies and curricula, a defense of the importance of Humanities in society, and the democratization of classrooms and schools to foster active participation in citizenship education.

The correlation between Citizenship Education and teaching methods in Social Sciences has become increasingly significant due to the growing interest from government institutions. This is driven by the recognition of new challenges and demands in preparing future citizens. In light of this concern, this article focuses on how social and civic competence is addressed in secondary education Social Sciences classrooms, within the context of specific teaching methods and learning environments. To achieve this, the article establishes the theoretical and epistemological foundations of Social Sciences teaching methods, which form the framework for examining democratic citizenship. These foundations primarily revolve around critical and active approaches.

Active citizenship recommends educating students to responsibly exercise active citizenship through participation in community affairs. Community service can be considered as a curricular instrument that guarantees that students, throughout their schooling, experience and lead in acts of civic engagement, and put their knowledge and skills at the service of the community to learn to be citizens through the exercise of active citizenship.

The active exercise of citizenship is essential to promote social skills and to appreciate the value of diversity, but is additionally important for the defense of common values in the face of all forms of discrimination (gender, age, beliefs, etc.) and intolerance (segregation, marginalization, exploitation, violence, etc.)

Nonetheless, there is a need for changes in both the context and internal operations of educational institutions to transform them into democratic centers that acknowledge the rights and responsibilities of all individuals involved. Research consistently highlights the importance of students cultivating their ability to be autonomous and accountable citizens through engaging in activities where they can apply their knowledge and assert their citizenship within the school environment. This enables them to establish connections between the knowledge acquired in social science classrooms and their practical experiences.

The correlation between citizenship education (social and civic competence) and the teaching and learning of history in Spain aligns with previous international research. Several studies concur in recognizing the potential of history as a discipline for addressing social and civic competence among students. These studies emphasize the importance of implementing innovative approaches, such as tackling relevant social issues, utilizing interactive learning methods, and fostering critical thinking and reflection. By incorporating these strategies, stereotypes and prejudices that hinder meaningful learning can be effectively diminished in a lasting manner.

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